

Visible Quantum Cutting in NaGdF₄:Eu Nanocrystals for Enhancing Solar Cell Efficiency

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NaGdF₄:Eu nanocrystals are known as quantum cutting systems, that can convert UV radiation into the visible range with a quantum yield close to 200%. Typically, 202 nm photons are used to excite the ⁶G_J levels of Gd³⁺ ions. However, this mechanism has drawbacks due to low absorption efficiency at 202 nm and the relatively large amount of absorbed energy, which dissipates through non-radiative transitions. Additionally, the absence of vacuum ultraviolet radiation in sunlight renders this quantum cutting method useless for designing any type of sunlight converters. In this study, we demonstrate the ability of NaGdF₄:5%Eu to convert 250 nm UV light into visible emission of Er³⁺ ions. We employ an alternative quantum cutting approach based on cross-relaxation between Er³⁺ ions, which exhibits a quantum yield of 188%. This technique offers promising prospects in the field of green photovoltaics.

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1. Introduction

The use of traditional fossil energy sources (coal, natural gas, and petroleum) in the power industry causes irreparable harm to the environment. The development and implementation of solar energy technologies is one of the most promising and competitive areas for solving the problem of energy supply to consumers by converting solar energy into electricity [1–5]. Solar energy contribution to global electricity generation is relatively small, amounting to 3.6% in 2022. By 2050, however, photovoltaic technologies are expected to provide about 25% of total electricity demand [6]. Nevertheless, despite advances in photovoltaic technology, the main drawback of solar panels is

their low efficiency [7, 8].

The spectral distribution of sunlight consists of photons with wide wavelength ranging from UV to IR radiation (280–2500 nm, 0.5–4.4 eV) [9]. However, modern photovoltaic panels use only a relatively small fraction of the solar photons, mainly in the long-wave part of the spectrum [10]. The energy of short-wave radiation is inefficiently used and released as heat during thermalization process. As a result, the maximum theoretical efficiency of silicon solar cells is 33.7% (the Shockley-Queisser limit). In effect, the efficiency of the most silicon solar panels doesn't exceed 20% [11].

The efficiency of solar cells can be drastically increased by depositing a quantum cutting material to their surface [12]. Quantum cutting (also known as down-conversion) is the process of absorbing a high-energy photon and emitting two or more photons of lower energy [13]. The quantum yield of such a process can significantly exceed 100%. Estimates of the efficiency of silicon photovoltaic cells modified with a down-

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conversion layer on the front surface are up to 38.6% [14].

The Gd³⁺-Eu³⁺ ion system is a prime candidate for efficient spectral conversion by the process of quantum cutting due to its rich energy level structure [15]. In such systems Gd³⁺ ions absorb one vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) photon at 202 nm while Eu³⁺ ions emit two photons of visible light (Fig. 1) [16–19]. In the first step, excitation of ⁶G_J level of Gd³⁺ ion results in energy transfer by cross-relaxation to the ⁵D₀ state of Eu³⁺ ion. In the second step, Gd³⁺ transfers the remaining excitation energy to another Eu³⁺ ion, which then undergoes fast cascade non-radiative relaxation to the ⁵D_J states. Both steps lead to the emission of a visible light due to ⁵D_J → ⁷F_J transitions of Eu³⁺ ions. It may seem that excitation at 394 nm can be used to calculate the quantum cutting efficiency as well. In this case, however, no cross-relaxation and no quantum cutting is observed, so for every ultraviolet photon absorbed one visible photon is emitted. A serious drawback of this quantum cutting mechanism is the absence of VUV light in the solar spectrum at Air Mass 1.5 and very low absorption efficiency at 202 nm. Therefore, it is necessary to propose an alternative quantum cutting mechanism capable of converting short-

wave radiation of sunlight into the visible light.

In this study, we consider and analyze the quantum cutting process through cross-relaxation of two adjacent Eu³⁺ ions in the NaGdF₄ nanocrystals synthesized by the hydrothermal method. Photoluminescence excitation and emission spectra were investigated to determine photophysical properties. For NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ nanoparticles the quantum yield of up to 188% was obtained.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

All materials were used as received without further purification. Gadolinium chloride hexahydrate (GdCl₃·6H₂O, 99%), europium chloride hexahydrate (EuCl₃·6H₂O, 99.9%) and oleic acid (C₁₈H₃₄O₂, 90%) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Sodium fluoride (NaF, 99%) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH, 99%) were purchased from JSC "Vecton" (Saint Petersburg, Russia). Cyclohexane was obtained from JSC "EKOS-1" (Moscow, Russia).

2.2. Preparation of NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ nanocrystals

The NaGdF₄ nanocrystals doped with 5 mol% of Eu³⁺ were synthesized by hydrothermal method using oleic acid as a stabilizing agent [20–22]. In a typical procedure, 1.2 g NaOH was first dissolved in 2 ml of distilled water, and then 8 ml ethanol and 20 ml oleic acid were added dropwise while stirring to form metal-oleic acid complexes. After vigorous stirring for 30 min, 0.95 mmol GdCl₃·6H₂O and 0.05 mmol EuCl₃·6H₂O (the total amount of rare earth metal salts is 1 mmol) were added to the resulting mixture. After dissolving the precursors, 8 ml of an aqueous solution of NaF with a concentration of 1.0 M were added to the solution. The resulting solution was stirred for 30 min to form a white foamy mixture, then placed in a Teflon-lined autoclave and heated at 190°C for 24 h. Lastly, autoclave

FIG. 1: Quantum cutting mechanisms for Gd³⁺-Eu³⁺ system under VUV excitation. The solid and dotted arrows represent radiative, non radiative transitions and interionic transitions, respectively.

was naturally cooled to room temperature. The precipitates of $\text{NaGdF}_4:5\%\text{Eu}^{3+}$ at the bottom were collected by centrifugation and washed several times with ethanol and deionized water to remove oleic acid and other residues. The samples thus obtained were dried in air at ambient temperature for 12 h and then placed in cyclohexane to prevent aggregation. To obtain a well-dispersed suspension of particles in cyclohexane, the solution was subjected to ultrasonic treatment.

2.3. Characterization

The X-ray-powder diffraction (XRD) measurement was carried out using a LANScientific Xrd-602 X-ray diffractometer with $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The measurement time was 5 s per 0.025° step and the diffraction angle range was 8° – 90° . The microstructural characteristics of the synthesized nanoparticles were examined using a Carl Zeiss EVO 50 XVP scanning electron microscope (SEM). The photoluminescence excitation and emission spectra were acquired using a Horiba Fluorolog QM-75-22-C modular spectrofluorimeter with an external 75 W xenon lamp as an excitation light source and registration using a Hamamatsu R13456 photomultiplier with a multi-alkali cathode. All the tests were performed at room temperature.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Crystal structure and morphology

The powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the NaGdF_4 nanocrystals doped with 5% Eu^{3+} were measured and are shown in Fig. 2. It can be clearly seen, that as-prepared phosphors exhibited fairly good crystallinity and all of the diffraction peaks can be readily indexed to the pure hexagonal $\beta\text{-NaGdF}_4$ fluoride crystallized in a $P\bar{6}$ space group. No other impurity reflexes were detected, indicating that the obtained particles were of high purity and Eu^{3+} doping

did not significantly change the crystal structure.

The size and morphology of $\text{NaGdF}_4:5\%\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanocrystals were characterized by scanning electron microscope (SEM). As shown in Fig. 3, the as-prepared nanophosphors have a spherical shape with rough surfaces and characteristic diameter distributed in the range 45–484 nm. The average size of hundreds of nanoparticles is about 145 nm.

3.2. Excitation and emission properties

Fig. 4A shows the excitation spectrum of NaGdF_4 nanocrystals doped with 5 mol% europium obtained by monitoring the $^5\text{D}_0 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_0$ emission of Eu^{3+} ions at 620 nm. There is a series of narrow absorption bands related to the characteristic f-f transitions of Gd^{3+} and Eu^{3+} ions. Bands peaked at 252, 273 and 310 nm correspond to the transitions from the ground $^8\text{S}_{7/2}$ state to the excited $^6\text{D}_J$, ($\sim 40,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) $^6\text{I}_J$ ($\sim 37,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $^6\text{P}_J$ ($\sim 32,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) states of Gd^{3+} ions. The $^7\text{F}_0 \rightarrow ^5\text{D}_3$ transition of Eu^{3+} ions corresponds to the excitation bands at 394 nm ($\sim 25,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). In addition, the band at 203 nm due to $^8\text{S}_{7/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{G}_J$ transition of Gd^{3+} ions was not observed because of low efficiency of the xenon lamp at

FIG. 2: Powder XRD pattern of the as-synthesized $\text{NaGdF}_4:5\%\text{Eu}^{3+}$ nanophosphors and the corresponding reference pattern of $\beta\text{-NaGdF}_4$.

200 nm. It is worth mentioning that the 252 and 273 nm quanta used to excite the Gd³⁺-Eu³⁺ system have energies of 40,000 and 37,000 cm⁻¹, respectively. This is two times higher than the photon energy of Eu³⁺ emission at 612 nm (~17,000 cm⁻¹) and therefore meet the requirements of the quantum cutting mechanism. The NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ emission spectra obtained at excitation wavelengths of 252, 273, and 394 nm are shown in Fig. 4B. The spectra are normalized to the ⁵D₁ → ⁷F_J emission intensity. The intense europium luminescence upon excitation at 252 and 273 nm implies energy transfer from Gd³⁺ ions to Eu³⁺ ions. Irradiation at 394 nm results in direct single-quantum excitation of Eu³⁺ ions via the ⁷F₀ → ⁵D₃ transition. All observed emission spectra upon excitation at 252 nm (blue line), 273 nm (green line) and 394 nm (red line) correspond to the transitions from the ⁵D_J (J = 0, 1, 2) excited levels to the ⁷F_J (J = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4) ground state of Eu³⁺ ions. As shown in Fig. 4B, NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ emission spectra vary significantly with excitation wavelength. Relative intensities of red luminescence from the upper ⁵D₀ level of Eu³⁺ are twice as strong under excitation at 252 nm as compared to direct excitation of Eu³⁺ ions at 394 nm. This fact demonstrates the higher yield of the quantum cutting effect as compared to simple down-shifting process. Interestingly, the normalized emission spectra upon excitation at 273 and 394 nm are practically identical. Thus, the 273 nm

FIG. 3: SEM image of the as-prepared NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ nanocrystals.

excitation of NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ nanocrystals does not lead to quantum cutting.

3.3. Alternative mechanism for quantum cutting in Gd³⁺ - Eu³⁺ system under 252 nm excitation

In contrast to the conventional quantum cutting process in the Gd³⁺ Eu³⁺ system which requires excitation by VUV radiation, we propose

FIG. 4: (A) The excitation spectrum of NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ monitored at 620 nm, the ⁵D₀ → ⁷F₂ transition of Eu³⁺. (B) Emission spectra of NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ upon excitation of the ⁶D_J and ⁶I_J states of Gd³⁺ at 252 nm (blue line), 273 nm (green line), respectively and upon excitation of the ⁵D₃ state of Eu³⁺ at 394 nm (red line). The emission spectra are normalized to the ⁵D₁ → ⁷F_J emission bands.

a different mechanism with excitation at longer wavelength. This mechanism is schematically shown in Fig. 5. After excitation at 252 nm, direct energy transfer occurs from the 6D_J level of Gd^{3+} ion to the resonant level of a nearby Eu^{3+} ion. In the next step, fast cross-relaxation takes place between the two neighboring Eu^{3+} ions. Then, cascade non-radiative multiphoton transitions populate the emissive ${}^5D_{0-3}$ levels of the first Eu^{3+} ion. According to the proposed energy transfer scheme in Fig. 5, both Eu^{3+} ions emit visible photons due to the ${}^5D_0 \rightarrow {}^7F_J$ transitions, which explains increased emission efficiency from 5D_0 upon excitation at 252 nm.

Experimentally, the quantum cutting efficiency can be estimated by comparing the emission due to quantum cutting with the emission due to any other process following direct excitation. For instance, excitation at 394 nm, as shown in Fig. 5 (right), results in luminescence corresponding to the ${}^5D_{0-3} \rightarrow {}^7F_J$ transition (see Fig. 4B). It should be noted that the energy of the 394 nm excitation ($\sim 25,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is not sufficient for the quantum cutting process to occur, and a much higher energy ($\sim 2 \times 17,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) is required to emit

two photons of red light. The quantum cutting efficiency QCE of the process presented in Fig. 5 can be defined as:

$$QCE = \frac{n_{CR}}{n_{ET}} \quad (1)$$

where n_{CR} is the number of photons emitted from the 5D_0 level, which is excited by cross-relaxation process between Eu^{3+} ions; and n_{ET} is the number of photons emitted due to the $Gd^{3+} \rightarrow Eu^{3+}$ direct energy transfer and the subsequent cascade non-radiative transitions. Since the emission is proportional to the number of photons, the expression (1) can be presented in form of

$$QCE = \frac{I_{CR}}{I_{ET}} \quad (2)$$

where I_{CR} and I_{ET} are integral emissions following the cross relaxation and the direct energy transfer processes, respectively. The value of I_{ET} one can calculate by using the luminescence spectrum measured upon 394 nm excitation and normalized to the intensities of the emissions from the ${}^5D_{1,2,3}$ levels. This normalization procedure formally provides equal powers for the direct excitation process and the direct energy transfer process, which populate the 5D_0 level. Therefore, we can set $I_{ET} = I_{394nm}$ in further calculation, where I_{394nm} is the normalized integral emission upon 394 nm excitation. Under these conditions, the I_{CR} intensity can be expressed as the difference between the normalized integral emissions upon excitations at 252 nm and 394 nm $I_{CR} = I_{252nm} - I_{394nm}$. So, the final expression for QCE is as follows:

$$QCE = \frac{I_{252nm} - I_{394nm}}{I_{394nm}} \quad (3)$$

The calculated value of QCE is about 0.88 for $NaGdF_4:5\%Eu^{3+}$. This indicates the probability of emitting a second red photon via the cross-relaxation mechanism between Eu^{3+} ions. Since the non-radiative relaxation of the 5D_0 state in $NaGdF_4:5\%Eu^{3+}$ nanocrystals is negligible compared to radiative transitions, the quantum

FIG. 5: Quantum cutting mechanisms for Gd^{3+} - Eu^{3+} system under UV radiation excitation (left). Direct excitation (DE) of Eu^{3+} ions by 394 nm radiation (right). The dashed and solid arrows represent cross-relaxation (CR), interionic energy transfer (ET) and radiative transitions, respectively.

yield of the Eu³⁺ emission due to the Gd³⁺ → Eu³⁺ direct energy transfer is very close to 100%. Overall quantum yield consists of two contributions due to the quantum cutting and the direct energy transfer. Therefore, in NaGdF₄:5%Eu³⁺ nanocrystals overall quantum yield reaches 188% at the 252 nm excitation at room temperature.

4. Conclusions

The hexagonal phase of NaGdF₄ nanocrystals, doped with 5 mol% Eu³⁺ ions, was synthesized using a hydrothermal method. As-synthesized phosphors exhibited bright red luminescence under excitation at 252 nm. A

comparative analysis revealed the alternative quantum cutting mechanism based on cross-relaxation between neighboring Er³⁺ ions, which led to a quantum yield of 188%. Thus, the realized conversion of 252 nm radiation into visible light is an important step towards increasing the efficiency of solar cells.

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